

as anti-cancer drugs has encouraged the advancement of modern therapeutic inorganic chemistry [10]. Second- and third-generation platinum (II) complexes have been developed by altering the cisplatin structure to include coordinated bond(s) with different features, such as basicity and electronic steric effects [11, 12]. Different generation of Platinum complex are given in Figure 2. These changes allow the complexes to interact with DNA via coordinate bonds.

Figure 2: Different generation of Platinum complex

IV. MECHANISM OF ACTION OF PLATINUM-BASED DRUGS

When Cisplatin, is administered intravenously, due to the relatively high (about 100 mM) concentration of chloride ion in the bloodstream it remains neutral and unchanged [13]. Then cisplatin can bind with plasma protein within 24 h of administration because cisplatin can bind with plasma proteins albumin, cysteine, transferrin etc. resulting deactivation of larger amount of applied cisplatin. Through passive diffusion and transport proteins, such as copper-transporter 1 (CTR1) and organic cation transporter OCT1-3 (organic cation transporter 1–3), the remaining active platinum compounds penetrate tumor cells [14, 15]. Then the platinum compounds get hydrated and subsequently forms $[\text{PtCl}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^+$ and $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$ respectively [16]. These species finally enter into nucleus and binds to DNA via intra or inter crosslinks causing DNA damage [17]. Simultaneously, in this process excessive reactive oxygen species (ROS) get produced and onset of apoptosis occurs. Similar mechanism of cytotoxicity also occurs in case of other platinum compounds like carboplatin, oxaliplatin, nedaplatin etc. Binding of Platinum (II) complex with DNA shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Binding of Platinum (II) complex with DNA

V. FUNCTIONALIZATION OF PLATINUM (II) COMPLEXES

Over the last few decades, researchers have become increasingly interested in attaching platinum-based medications to various functional molecules or nanoparticles, both with and without targeting functions [18,19]. The functionalization of platinum-based drugs has a number of potential benefits, including (i) increased drug concentration specifically within the target area [20]; (ii) increased bioactivity, which can enable theranostic applications [21]; and (iii) the possibility of unified pharmacokinetics across diverse functional molecules [22]. Pharmaceuticals based on functionalised platinum so offer a potential way to overcome the limitations of Pt-based drugs, enhance the effectiveness of diagnostic agents, and eventually enable more accurate and thorough diagnostic capabilities. Functionalised platinum-based medications can also be used as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) contrast agents or fluorescent probes [23].

VI. PLATINUM (IV) PRODRUGS

Various strategies have been employed to limit the side effects, including modifications of platinum drugs [24], using prodrugs [25], carriers such as heparin [26], antibodies [27], pH-, temperature-, and ultrasound-responsive hydrogels [28], silk [29], functionalized and self-assembled nanoparticles [30], liposomes, multilamellar liposomes [31], engineered exosomes [32], peptides [33], and dendrimers [34]. Despite these strategies, cancer cells often display increased resistance to platinum-based drugs [35]. To overcome these challenges, Pt(IV) prodrugs have been developed, which have many advantages over Pt(II) drugs [36]. Due to inertness and slower ligand exchange of Pt(IV) prodrugs off-target reactions get reduced and thus the concentration of the active drugs increases. Pt(IV) prodrugs are less reactive with biomolecule than the Pt(II) compounds. In cancer cells under appropriate conditions Pt(IV) prodrugs are reduced to Pt(II) compounds, which then binds to DNA [37]. During this reduction process Platinum losses ligand from the coordination sphere and coordination no changes from 6 to 4, which may have additional pharmacological effects [38]. In this Pt(IV) prodrugs to Pt(II) conversion bioreductants plays vital role. This six-coordinate octahedral molecular geometry in Pt(IV) offers improved kinetic stability as well as many pharmacological activities such as lipophilicity, redox stability, tumor selectivity, and improved bioactivity [39]. However, the exact mechanism of Pt(IV) prodrugs is not clear [40]. Because Pt(II) reduction is thought to be necessary before these can interact with their intended biological targets, they are referred to as prodrugs. Clinical trials have assessed a number of cisplatin analogues that have been converted into Pt(IV) complexes. According to these findings, Pt(IV) complexes have several advantages over cisplatin, including oral availability and less adverse effects [41, 42].

VII. FUNCTIONALIZATION OF PLATINUM (IV) COMPLEXES

Hydroxido, chlorido, and acetato are often utilized as axial ligands in clinical studies to change the pharmacokinetics of Pt(IV) prodrugs [43]. To block various enzymes and processes involved in cancer cell growth, bioactive ligands have been included into Pt(IV)-ligand conjugates [44]. This strategy also has the advantage of having a unified pharmacokinetic effect to increase the possibility that the bioactive ligand and cytotoxic Pt(II) cargo will work together to improve chemotherapy efficacy.

VIII. NANOMATERIALS AS DRUG CARRIERS

Nanocarrier-based platinum drug delivery systems offer a viable alternative to conventional platinum medicines [45]. Gold nano clusters (GNCs) have gained popularity as drug transport carriers in recent years due to their strong photostability [46], water solubility, and biocompatibility [47]. Compared to ordinary nanoparticles, GNCs typically have a particle size of less than 2 nm and a longer blood circulation period. Pt medicines can be efficiently loaded in GNCs and accumulate in tumor tissues because to the enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect, resulting in greater therapeutic efficacy and less systemic toxicity. Furthermore, ultrasmall GNCs are typically eliminated from the body due to ineffective renal clearance, showing good metabolism and biocompatibility. Superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPIONs) as drug carriers are very important due to their advantages of low toxicity, biocompatibility, biodegradability, and well water dispersion. [48]. Other important nanomaterials as drug carriers are Mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs) [49,50], organic polymeric nanoparticles etc. Pt drugs encapsulated in polymeric nanoparticles reduce the side effects without affecting drug efficacy.

IX. PT NANOCLUSTERS (PT NCS) AS A NEW PT DRUG FOR CANCER THERAPY

Pt NCs have received a lot of attention in bioanalysis and biomedicine due to their unique physicochemical properties, including as ultra-small size, exact structure, photoluminescence, X-ray absorption, minimal cytotoxicity, and high biocompatibility [51,52]. Pt NCs, in particular, offer promising anti-cancer applications due to their unusual molecular composition and high biological safety profile. These very surface-active Pt NCs are impacted by internal acidic organelles such as endosomes and lysosomes, and they rapidly disintegrate to generate oxidative Pt states that can adhere to and alter DNA structure, resulting in cancer cell death. Furthermore, ultra small Pt NCs can bind to the grooves of the DNA double helix, causing further DNA damage. Thus, eliminating cancer cells using Pt NC-based nano-drugs appears to have a synergistic impact of both Pt NCs and Pt ions that cause DNA damage.

X. FUTURE PERSPECTIVES AND CONCLUSION

Pt-based anti-cancer medicines serve an important role in clinical cancer therapy, with satisfactory efficacy. Cisplatin and other first-line clinical platinum anti-cancer medications are relatively ancient pharmaceuticals with a known molecular mechanism for treating malignancies. The side effects severely limit the use of platinum anticancer medicines. As a result, researchers have looked into improved Pt-based medicines that could boost anti-cancer efficacy while reducing systemic toxicity. Pt NC-based nano-drugs have received a lot of interest due to their intrinsic longer blood circulation duration, EPR effect, and ease of surface functionalization. Continued research into the cellular and molecular pathways involved will provide insights into new therapeutic targets and strategies for the development of more effective and targeted platinum-based therapies.

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